

Zero-Energy Brewery

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In association with DTU Foods desire to attain a new building, dedicated to their brewery division, we are designing an unconventional, flexible and inviting small zero-energy building, where the generic energy designs of the building contribute to a green beer-production. The goal is to obtain a building with as low an energy consumption as possible (zero-energy building), accommodate the functions that DTU Food demand, a great indoor climate and have a significant and inviting aesthetic expression.